

DYES DERIVED FROM THIOHYDANTOIN. PART III.

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In continuation of the previous work thiohydantoin has been condensed with aliphatic and aromatic ketones and quinones with acetic anhydride as condensing agent. The condensation products have been isolated in keto-form.

In previous communications thiohydantoin has been condensed with a number of nitroso and isonitroso compounds (Pendse and Dutt, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 953), and with aromatic aldehydes (Namjoshi and Dutt, *ibid.*, 1931, 8, 241; Ghosh, *ibid.*, 1934, 11, 27). To complete this series of investigations thiohydantoin has been condensed with aliphatic and aromatic ketones and quinones using acetic anhydride as the condensing agent.

With acetic anhydride unstable acetyl derivatives, presumably of the type (II) are generally formed, which are, however, very easily hydrolysed by dilute alkalis (or by boiling water) to the free keto types (I).

On account of the difficulty of purification of the acetyl derivatives due to their unstable nature, the condensation products described in this paper have been obtained in the free keto-form (I). As is expected the condensation products are less coloured than those obtained with aldehydes and much less than with nitroso and isonitroso compounds. Where there are more than one keto groups in the compound, it has been observed that only one molecule of the ketone or quinone condenses with one molecule of thiohydantoin,

The following ketones have been condensed: with thiohydantoin. (1) phenanthraquinone, (2) tetramethyldiamidobenzophenone (3) acenaphthoquinone, (4) isatin, (5) fluorenone, (6) alizarin, (7) benzil, (8) dibenzylideneacetone, (9) *p*-benzoquinone and (10) anthraquinone.

Unsuccessful attempts were also made to condense the following:—

(1) Acetone, (2) methylpropylketone, (3) diethylketone, (4) *cyclo*-pentanone, (6) coumarin, (7) acetophenone.

Most of the condensation products are crystalline substances, and dye beautiful light shades on wool and silk.

EXPERIMENTAL.

5-Phenanthraquinonethiohydantoin.—A mixture of thiohydantoin (1.16 g.), phenanthraquinone (2 g.) and acetic anhydride (about 15 c.c.) was heated under reflux for about 1 hour. The reaction which was very vigorous at first gradually subsided and it was complete when the mixture assumed a brownish yellow shade. The mixture was cooled and then poured into water when a brown precipitate came down. This was filtered off, washed with hot water and crystallised from alcohol.

TABLE I.

(Thiohydantoin = T.		M.p.	Wave-length of absorption shadow.	Analysis.	
Name.	Appearance.			Fonnd.	Required
5-Phenanthraquinone-T	Greenish brown needles	146°	4513Å	S, 10.23%	10.46
5-Tetramethyldiamino- benzophenone-T	Light yellow needles	166°	4450	9.16	8.75
5-Acenaphthoquinone-T	Chocolate brown powder	Above. 260°	4695	11.20	11.43
5-Isatin-T	Reddish brown prisms	„	4764	13.36	13.73
5-Fluorenone-T	Greyish yellow needles	102°	4410	11.72	11.41
(1:2-Dihydroxyanthra- quinone-T	Yellowish green prisms	157°	5600	9.79	9.47
5-Alizarin-T					
5-Benzil-T or	Greenish yellow flakes	93°	4630	10.64	10.39
5-Dibenzylideneacetone-T	Light brown flakes	113°	4710	9.23	9.58
5- <i>p</i> -Benzoquinone-T	Orange-brown needles	136°	4875	15.64	15.83
5-Anthraquinone-T	Light yellow flakes	167°	4890	10.37	10.46

Condensations of thiohydantoin with other ketones were similarly carried out with very slight modifications to suit individual cases. In general the condensation products are fairly soluble in ethyl and methyl alcohol, ethyl acetate, chloroform, and sparingly soluble in benzene, ether and carbon tetrachloride. Mineral acids dissolve the substances giving yellow to orange coloured solutions from which the original substances can be precipitated by addition of water. When to the alcoholic solutions of these dyes a little caustic soda is added the colour in many cases is considerably intensified. In several cases the substances can be precipitated by addition of dilute acids from dilute solution in alkali. The compounds are described in Table I.

The author takes the opportunity of expressing his indebtedness to Dr. S. Dutt of the Allahabad University for his valuable guidance and the interest he took in this work and to the authorities of the Victoria College, Gwalior, for the facilities given to him during the progress of this work.

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Received April 9, 1938.

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